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Physical Computing: A low-cost project-based approach to engineering education

P. K. Hannon

TU Dublin, Ireland

D. Berry

TU Dublin, Ireland

S. Chance

TU Dublin, Ireland; UCL, United Kingdom

M. Core

TU Dublin, Ireland

F. Duignan

TU Dublin, Ireland

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One of the current trends in engineering education, often due to costs, is to use simulation software for the design and analysis of systems. However, using simulation packages as an alternative to real-world equipment may lead to a lack of student engagement and confidence, thereby reducing the impact of learning. This workshop presents an alternative mode of module delivery that facilitates practice-based learning, where students get hands-on practical computing using inexpensive, yet real-world equipment and technologies that can help transform notional self-directed learning to actual learning.

In this workshop, participants will discuss the philosophy, rationale, and techniques used to teach Physical Computing at one Technological University. The workshop will be broken into 5 sections, a timeline for which is presented below.

Suggested timeline for each section of the workshop

- | | |
|--|--------------|
| 1. Philosophy & example modules | (10 minutes) |
| 2. Case study module details | (10 minutes) |
| 3. Walkthrough implementation | (30 minutes) |
| 4. Breakout discussion with participants | (30 minutes) |
| 5. Summary of results from section 4 | (10 minutes) |

Section 1: Philosophy & example modules delivered using the approach

To begin, workshop facilitators will introduce their project-based philosophy and approach to teaching Physical Computing by briefly describing a range of modules delivered using the approach in their school: **Robo Sumo/RoboSlam** (a robot-building challenge); **Build a PC** (a highly practical introduction to computer architecture); **Embedded Systems** (a highly practical look at microprocessor and microcontroller systems).

Section 2: Case study module details

During this section the facilitators will describe in more detail how they conceived, reconfigured, and redeployed a conventional undergraduate **Internet of Things (IoT)** module using the problem based approach to reach a broader and more diverse audience using the four design principles outlined in [1] to:

- a) eliminate barriers—often encountered when delivering modules that involve the integration of several hardware, software and communication components;
- b) achieve critical affect—by removing the frustrations involved in significant management overhead of configuration and maintenance involved when using open-source software;
- c) guide towards independence—by providing prescriptive instructions for a sample application and guides towards further expansion for continued self-directed learning; and
- d) ensure scalability—by publishing detailed instructions on-line and providing sample inexpensive project kits to workshop participants in order to facilitate the delivery of the material by third parties outside specialised laboratory environments.

Section 3: Walkthrough implementation of the proposed approach

In this section, the participants will be guided through a practical implementation of a case study that uses the proposed approach for teaching a physical computing module in order to gain hands on experience of the approach. The participants will be guided through the design and implementation approach used to build a series of structured mini projects, involving the integration of inexpensive but disparate, real-world hardware, communications and open-source software components, building to a complete end to end solution for a real world IoT application. Assessments methods used in the module and the level of student engagement with the approach will be presented as part of this section.

Section 4: Breakout discussion with participants

During this section, participants will be asked to:

- Describe cost-effective ways to balance value and overhead associated with a problem-based engineering approach
- Identify and evaluate mechanisms for using real-world technologies for module delivery as opposed to the more de facto approach of using simulation software
- Discuss their hands-on experience of using the approach to develop a real world IoT application involving the integration of several disparate hardware and software components
- Discuss assessments methods and tools suitable when using this teaching approach
- Appraise the merits of the approach to facilitate building students' competence and confidence with using real world technologies
- Discuss the merits of the approach for removing the barriers to entry for learners in engaging with new technologies and for inspiring further self-directed learning.
- Discuss the impact of some teaching and learning "patterns" used in delivering the pilot module such as: "Repeat after me"; "Here's a solution for 'X'. Please use the approach to solve 'Y'"; "Here's a worked example A and some similar problems. Keep trying until you get all the correct answers."; "Change this and see what happens"; "This is broken in this way - fix it"; "This is broken in some way, find the problem and fix it"
- Identify implications of the overall approach for teaching and learning in engineering education

Section 5: Summary of results from section 4

A summary of the results from section 4 will be compiled in this section. This will serve as a foundation for the further development and assessment of the approach.

Overall, this workshop provides the rationale for “holding the line” against the *de facto* approach of using simulation software at the expense of practical and problem-based engineering activities. The approach is particularly relevant for modules that involve the integration of several hardware, software and communication components.

- [1] T. Burke, D. Berry, and S. Chance, Reaching new audiences through "RoboSlam!" workshops, 2013